

"YOUTH EDUCATION IN DRESS CULTURE"
(EDUCATION AND IMMORTAL CULTURE OF THE PEOPLE)

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ANNOTATION: This article focuses on the clothing culture and education of the youth, the clothing styles of the Central Asian and European people, the modern (T-shirts with various silly writings and pictures, shorts and slippers), the immortal culture of the people shines brightly, and the morals of the people.

KEY WORDS: clothing culture of young people, clothing styles of Central Asian people, clothing styles of European people, T-shirt, shorts and slippers, immortal culture of the people.

Dress culture reveals a person's appearance, spiritual world, aesthetics, moral qualities and potential. The attitude towards the culture of dressing is also a factor that expresses the views of a person regarding beauty, elegance, and manners. It is worth noting that in today's rapidly developing global era, both clothes and the attention and demand for clothing are changing.

Dressing well is also a unique art. Good taste is manifested first of all in matching clothes. Tailored clothes can be suitable for a certain situation, according to a person's occupation, event, environment, etc., and can be stylish depending on the time and place.

Fashion is understood as a custom of dressing according to the tastes and tastes of a certain social group and people for a certain period of time. Fashion is not only a change of clothes, but also a search for a unique aesthetic style, a way of walking, a manifestation of taste and internal culture. Fashion has a long history. Many experts believe that the fashion was born in the XIV century. The main headdress of Turkic women was a hat, scarf, shoes, khavush, underwear-shirt, outerwear-shorts, camisole, nimcha, cloak. So, in fact, is "fashion" spoiling our youth? What prevents them from dressing according to our national traditions? Or should fashion be banned? What is the concept of fashion in general? Who are their initiators? Is it only young people who are hungry for new things that are responsible for the change or destruction of the dressing culture?

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Clothing is a human ornament. Clothing changes as times change. Different colors, long-short, narrow-wide, luxurious-unsightly, expensive-cheap clothes. For many people, it is not important whether these clothes fit, whether they are suitable for their age, figure, or not. What's new has to be worn, that's all. This is the demand of "Moda". Recently, there has been a lot of talk about the dressing culture of our youth. Most of them express harsh and objectionable opinions about the honor of young people. The fact that some young men and women blindly follow the footsteps of fashion, their clothing is moving away from national traditions, the interest in tight, short, revealing clothes is increasing, these customs are being criticized as being contrary to Uzbekism. Of course, there is soul in such a relationship. In fact, the way young people dress has changed in recent times. This kind of situation makes one think.

So, in fact, is "fashion" spoiling our youth? What prevents them from dressing according to our national traditions? Or should fashion be banned? What is the concept of fashion in general? Who are their initiators? Is it only young people who are hungry for new things that are responsible for the change or destruction of the dressing culture? In order to clarify this problem, let's share our opinions.

First of all, what role do clothes play in human life? It is not for nothing that the question is asked in this way. Because every person should know the benefits and harms of the clothes he wears, what kind of fabric they are made of, if necessary, their history and significance. No one ever hangs on the right fabric. Dressing has aspects related to human psyche, character, mood, upbringing, and taste. It should be noted here that clothing and customs did not appear by themselves. There is no definitive conclusion about when clothes appeared in human society. If we look at the clothing culture of our ancestors, we can see that their clothes and jewelry were unique and colorful. In general, the clothes of each period were considered to be a reflection of the culture of that time in a certain sense. That is, depending on the dress, one can think about the dressing manners and culture of the people of each era.

If you pay attention to the young people on the street, for example, our girls wear tight pants, open blouses, long and narrow skirts with open sides, wide hems, and short skirts. And our boys wear white, red, purple, green trousers, various sleeved and sleeveless t-shirts, shorts above the knee. The problem is that most of our young people don't even think about what kind of clothes to wear and what suits their height. If everyone knows what suits their height, body and facial structure, hair, eyes, skin color, figure, they will not follow fashion blindly. Moreover, there are experts in this field to help them. They give recommendations

taking into account the above norms when advertising new seasonal clothes or when speaking about fashion in the press, radio, and television.

The clothes worn by our young people do not affect their behavior, behavior, behavior, and the words that come out of their mouths. As a result, sometimes inappropriate words and actions arouse discontent among the public. Every person is perfected in the family. He has parents, grandparents, aunts and uncles who investigate around him. But sometimes they allow their daughters to wear tight pants, short skirts or clothes with open shoulders and stomachs so that they don't get left behind. In addition, in a certain sense, the environment in the family and school is also the reason for this. It is unfortunate that the family itself demands to wear such clothes, to be "modern". Everyone has their own taste and understanding. The most important thing is to be able to properly educate this taste and understanding, which will decorate a person and make him more beautiful. The public, that is, you and we are all educators.

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